

DEEP GATEWAY SWITCHING

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Abstract

This paper deals with the problem of data-enhanced gateway switching technique in high throughput satellite systems. Feeder links deployed in high frequency bands (i.e. Ka band or higher) suffer from substantial link quality degradation due to atmospheric events, specially rain. In order to solve this problem, operators deploy redundant gateways in different locations with the aim of configuring the best set of gateways in case of strong fading event occur in any of the teleport locations. In an operational environment, this switch is neither seamless nor instantaneous and non-negligible time-to-switch and switching times appear. As a result, the switching process requires to be pre-emptive and anticipate those fading events. With external prediction meteorological data, we build a data-based model able to predict a gateway outage and, therefore, when the switch shall be implemented. The mathematical model boils down to be a non-linear online regression problem. Numerical results show the performance of the system with real operational data.

1 Introduction

Due to the increasing capacity demands of satellite users, satellite missions have been deployed on high frequencies pushing the feeder links into even higher frequency bands. In those bands (Ka, Q/V) meteorological effects have a tremendous impact on the communication link. Indeed, rain attenuation could decay the received signal power strength from a few dBs to dozens.

This is first mentioned in a scientific paper in [1] and posteriorly further evaluated in [2], [3] and [4]. According to these mentioned works there exist different approaches to tackle gateway diversity. Among them, the current operational technique is the known as ‘N+P’ which consists of ‘N’ operational satellite gateways supported by ‘P’ redundant ones. Mission planning efficiently consider the geographical location of the teleports in order to statistically maintain the system outage below a certain threshold.

Indeed, the mentioned ‘N+P’ assumes that in case a teleport suffers from an excess of attenuation, the control centre will be able to swap its operation by one of the redundant gateways. As a general statement, this operational switch requires certain delay and, in particular, switches shall be planned dozens of minutes in advance. As a consequence,

operators must have a pre-emptive switching tool able to plan required switches. A normal operation is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 (a) 3+1 gateway configuration, one of the gateways suffer from rain event, (b) The gateway that suffered from rain is substituted by one with better conditions.

Bearing in mind that excess attenuation in the next tens of minutes is governed by rain events [5], the problem of predicting switches yields to a meteorological prediction problem.

While there exist ultra-local short-term meteorological products for applications like airport availability and Formula One planning, inferring link satellite link quality from rain

prediction has not been tackled before. As a matter of fact, in this problem two different models are merged. On the one hand, rain prediction models do not only rely on radar nowcasting techniques but other atmospheric parameters. Despite some companies claim to provide this very precise sub-hour and sub-km accumulated rain prediction, it is known that major inaccuracies appear. On the other hand, despite local precipitation is the main factor for determining outage attenuation events, fading will depend on the rain impacting the overall slant path range (i.e. the virtual road between the Earth station and the satellite). Consequently, in relatively high latitude location where elevation angles are low, the local rain prediction has a partial impact on the total attenuation.

In this paper we focus on inference problem of the outage event of a given teleport location based on rain prediction and actual link quality values. Considering that teleports are equipped with a power control mechanism that can compensate up to 10 dB of fading, we conceive a model able to infer the time duration that the link will be under this threshold. In other words, given the rain prediction in a given location we train a regression model able to establish under a certain probability, the duration of the outage. This predicted value will serve as an item for determining whether a switch shall take place or not.

The goal is to revisit the seminal work described in [6] which used a Bayesian approach for inferring the percentage of outage time and consider data-based machine learning techniques. It is important to remark that prediction models embedded radar data for short-term forecasting so that we do not consider the direct usage of radar images as in [7]. Indeed, we plan to consider data-based models in order to extend physical model-based techniques developed before [8].

The reminder of the paper is as follows. Section 2 describes the problem tackled and some hints of the problem solved. Section 3 describes the results and Section 4 concludes.

2. Methodology

2.1 Problem Formulation

Due to operational reasons the switching process is neither seamless nor immediate. In particular, it is assumed a certain *timeToReact* defined as the time delay between when the operator decides to perform the switch and when the switching process takes place. During the switching process, the service becomes unavailable during a period of time of *inactivePeriod*. Bearing this in mind, the conceived prediction model shall not only provide a configuration based on current link gateway qualities, but it shall intelligently determine whether the switch decision yields to a capacity performance gain. This involves the estimation of the percentage of outage time in the following hour.

In light of the above discussion, it is clear that the controller shall have access to future quality link values. In particular, the feature of interest is the average link quality over the evaluation period. Obviously, this value is uncertain at the time the decision has to be made so that inference (prediction) techniques shall be employed in order properly design the technique.

It is important to remark that the delays (*timeToReact* and *inactivePeriod*) are determined to be between tens of minutes, so that the evaluation period shall be long enough to incorporate these effects. In addition, we cannot rely on time series prediction as it is well known that propagation events have a low temporal correlation (at least less than one minute) and, statistically, gateway link quality samples with a time lag of few minutes will be completely uncorrelated. Therefore, it is necessary to rely on long-term statistics and the use of external data such as weather forecast as it is known that rain fading is the most important effect.

2.2 Datasets

For rain forecast we use the services of OpenWeather API [9] which provides an estimation of the rainfall rate for the next hour with minute granularity. Attending to the description of the webpage, weather models rely on deep learning techniques and local ground stations using different data sources. As it happens in similar products, there is no access to historical weather predictions and it is necessary to retrieve data from the server during the operational time. We did this during April 2022 until July 2022.

Link quality data is obtained via probing the teleport beacon level working in current operations. The time granularity is 5 minutes, and it is well calibrated so that measurements at 0 dBs mean the link is working at its nominal value. Alternatively, the teleport is equipped with an open loop power control able to mitigate fading effects below 10 dBs.

2.3 Data-enhanced model

In light of the above discussion, the prediction model consists of predicting the elapsed time the link quality is below a certain threshold. Mathematically we aim to predict

$$f(\rho) = \hat{\tau}, \quad (1)$$

being ρ the vector containing the predicted accumulated rain for the next temporal horizon and $\hat{\tau}$ the estimated time the link will be below the threshold under the same temporal horizon.

Clearly, the model is a well-known supervised regression technique. Indeed, it is necessary a training set of

$$\{\rho, \tau\} \quad (2)$$

in order to perform the regression process. Let us details some aspects relevant to the learning process.

The model shall be able to easily adapt to weather prediction models. Indeed, as for this specific case we have no control on the available model for weather prediction and it could vary over the operational life of the satellite.

Despite there are known models (i.e. ITU-R) that relate rainfall rate and attenuation, in here we cannot use those models as we do not have access to the overall rainfall over the slant path. In addition, ITU-R techniques work well in yearly average but present certain problems in instantaneous attenuation predictions [4].

Bearing this in mind, we construct a non-parametric non-linear regression model able to accurately predict the outage time.

3 Results

The conceived model is generated via real operational data form a satellite teleport located in Cagliari, Italy. The employed data ranges from April 2022 until July 2022.

Fig. 2 Predicted outage time versus ground truth

The model considers a non-parametric technique based on well-known k-nearest-neighbours and a temporal embedding of the rain prediction.

As depicted in Fig. 2 the model predicts rain events in 5 out of 6 reported cases during the considered time. The mean square error of the estimated outage duration is 2.2 minutes which is acceptable for the application under study. Remarkably, the tool has some false alarm events with little outage temporal values.

4 Conclusion

This paper analysed a data-based technique able to predict outages in satellite gateway links. Supported by an external service of rain prediction, a machine learning model that fusions the rain prediction and the link quality is build.

Numerical results show that under operational constraints, the tools properly estimates the duration of the outage events. This is shown to be useful for the gateway switching process in ‘N+P’ satellite missions.

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